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5

6 **Plant affinity to extreme soils and foliar sulphur mediate species-specific**
7 **responses to sheep grazing in gypsum systems**

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21 **ABSTRACT**

22 **Background:** Plants growing on extreme soils have mainly been described in relation to
23 their adaptations to edaphic conditions, although herbivores may also be an important
24 factor in these ecosystems. Gypsum soils occur in drylands often where livestock
25 practices occur. However, it is unknown whether plant traits related to gypsum soil
26 constraints are associated with resistance to herbivory.

27 **Aims:** In order to assess whether gypsum exclusive species might be favoured at higher
28 grazing levels and to detect the traits involved, we evaluated the responses of gypsum
29 exclusive vs. generalist plant species to three intensities of livestock pressure.

30 **Methods:** We analysed the relative cover shifts of species along a livestock gradient, and
31 variation in canopy height, canopy area, leaf carbon (C), nitrogen (N), and sulphur (S), specific
32 leaf area (SLA) and leaf dry matter content (LDMC).

33 **Results:** We found that gypsum-exclusive species responded by increasing or maintaining their
34 cover at medium and high grazing pressure, whereas most generalists responded by decreasing
35 it. Gypsum-exclusive species showed higher leaf S than generalists, regardless of grazing
36 intensity. All species showed similar patterns for canopy and leaf traits linked to loss of above-
37 ground biomass when grazing increased.

38 **Conclusions:** Plant affinity to gypsum soils mediates vulnerability to grazing with foliar S
39 possibly being a defence trait.

40 **KEYWORDS:** elemental composition, functional traits, gypsum soils, gypsophiles,
41 herbivory, semiarid systems

42 **Introduction**

43 Saline, gypsum and serpentine soils owing to their harsh physico-chemical features
44 limit plant life to adapted taxa (Kazakou et al. 2008; Munns and Tester 2008; Moore et
45 al. 2014). In these extreme soils, many species have traits to cope with their singular
46 edaphic characteristics (Mota et al. 2017). Plant traits have been extensively studied in

47 saline and serpentine soils, but have received less attention in gypsum soils (Palacio and
48 Escudero 2014), even though gypsum soils are widespread in drylands around the world
49 (Escudero et al. 2015).

50 The uniqueness of gypsum soils, which contain high concentrations of calcium
51 sulphate dihydroxide ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$), is linked to their high ionic concentrations of
52 calcium and sulphate in the soil solution, saturating the cation exchange complex of
53 soils and resulting in low nutrient retention and availability (Guerrero-Campo et al.
54 1999; Casby-Horton et al. 2015). Thus, plant communities growing on gypsum soils are
55 composed of species showing stress-tolerant traits (Hodgson et al. 1994), as gypsum
56 affects plant mineral nutrition and ultimately limits plant growth (Cera et al. 2021).
57 Plants on gypsum soils can be classified as gypsum exclusive and generalist species
58 (Palacio et al. 2007). The two groups differ in their affinity for gypsum and in several
59 plant traits. Mainly, they differ in their nutritional strategy to cope with the strong
60 nutrient imbalances typical of gypsum soils (Cera et al. 2022a), which affect their leaf
61 traits (Cera et al. 2021). Gypsum exclusive species are mainly restricted to gypsum
62 soils, accumulate in their leaves elements found in excess in gypsum soils (e.g., S and
63 Ca; Merlo et al. 2019), have low concentrations of N and P (Muller et al. 2017), and low
64 values of leaf dry matter content (LDMC) and carbon (C) (Cera et al. 2021). In contrast,
65 generalist species grow also on other soils different from gypsum ones, show lower
66 foliar S and Ca content, and avoid the translocation of elements found in excess in the
67 soil to above-ground organs (Cera et al. 2022a). However, these trait differences do not
68 seem to be solely linked to the edaphic affinity for gypsum, because gypsum exclusive
69 species do not show a nutritional requirement for gypsum (Cera et al. 2021). It is
70 therefore necessary to understand the impact of abiotic and biotic factors other than soil,
71 such as animal disturbance, to understand trait variation in gypsum plants.

72 Ecosystems with extreme soils are generally open landscapes (Escudero et al.
73 2015) that may have been subjected to livestock and wild ungulate pressure since the
74 Miocene (23 Ma) until today (Gordon and Prins 2019). Ungulates affect plants directly
75 by consuming their biomass (Huntly 1991). However, ungulates may also have indirect
76 effects on plant life by alleviating competition between plants (Noy-Meir et al. 1989),
77 providing limiting nutrients as N and P to soils (Sitters and Andriuzzi 2019),
78 compacting soil by trampling (Moret-Fernández et al. 2011), and creating spatial
79 heterogeneity. In addition, the effects of ungulates are intensified when soil resources
80 are scarce and plant biomass productivity is low (Cingolani et al. 2005), as frequently
81 occurs in extreme soils on drylands. Despite these theoretical constraints, there is
82 evidence that some plants adapted to extreme soils are favoured under herbivory over
83 other invasive or generalist species (Meyer and García-Moya 1989; Bonis et al. 2005;
84 Beck et al. 2015). However, the responses of plants growing in ecosystems with
85 extreme soils and under livestock pressure have been little studied (Pueyo et al. 2008,
86 Cera et al. 2022b). Thus, we do not know whether species adapted to environments with
87 extreme soils are also adapted to livestock pressure and the extent of variation in trait
88 responses because of that adaptation.

89 Wild and livestock ungulates alter the relative abundances of plant species (Noy-
90 Meir et al. 1989), affecting diversity. This is because they exhibit different preferences
91 for plant species (Gordon and Prins 2019) and plants vary in their resistance to animal
92 disturbance (Díaz et al. 2007). Consequently, some plant species decrease in abundance
93 in response to increased livestock pressure, whereas others increase in abundance or
94 remain unchanged (Cingolani et al. 2005). These groups of species with different
95 vulnerability to herbivory may display different traits to cope with the effects of
96 herbivory (Violle et al. 2007). Several plant traits are subject to selection under animal

97 disturbance (Díaz et al. 2007). Following the growth-defence trade-off hypothesis
98 (Herms and Mattson 1992), these traits can be included in two major responses of
99 herbivory-resistance strategies. First, tolerance to herbivory, which results in high
100 investment to growth to overcome biomass losses, and second, avoidance with main
101 investment in defences, such as spines, lignified leaves and stems, or chemical
102 compounds (Noy-Meir et al. 1989), discouraging herbivores from consuming plants
103 (Briske and Richards 1995).

104 In contrast, a tolerance strategy to herbivores implies high seed production and
105 rapid growth rates to compensate for biomass loss (Grime 2006), with high values of
106 leaf N and specific leaf area (SLA), but not LDMC and C, as proposed by the leaf
107 economic spectrum (Wright et al. 2004). In extreme soils, species with slow growth
108 rates dominate due to resource limitation inherent to the substrate. In addition, they
109 usually have a high investment in grazing avoidance traits and defence to herbivory
110 (Coley et al. 1985), as they are unable to recover lost biomass before being consumed
111 again due to their slow recovery rates (Strauss and Boyd 2011). High defence costs can
112 lead to trade-offs in plant competitiveness (Fine et al. 2006), restricting plant
113 distribution to extreme environments and favouring habitat specialisation (Fine et al.
114 2004; Rajakaruna 2018). Hence, the role of livestock in plant responses on extreme soils
115 should consider responses of species with different edaphic affinities and different
116 abilities to cope with herbivory when growing on extreme soils.

117 Plant communities on gypsum soils frequently support extensive sheep and goat
118 husbandry around the world (Pueyo et al. 2008; Akhiani 2015). Sheep and goats are
119 medium sized mixed feeders (Gordon and Prins 2019) with little selectivity for forage
120 species (Augustine and McNaughton 1998). Braun-Blanquet and Bolòs (1958) have
121 suggested that gypsum exclusive species might be favoured by moderate livestock

122 pressure on gypsum soils, because grazing exacerbates the restrictive conditions of
123 gypsum soils (Braun-Blanquet and Bolòs 1958). Therefore, herbivory, together with
124 edaphic factors, may play a major role in the ecology of gypsum exclusive species. It
125 has been suggested that foliar S accumulation could be an advantageous strategy under
126 herbivore pressure as a defence strategy (Cera et al. 2022a), which would explain why
127 species with foliar S could be favoured by livestock grazing. However, species-level
128 responses in terms of trait variability at different livestock pressure intensities have not
129 yet been evaluated in detail in ecosystems on gypsum soils.

130 The objective of this study was to quantify the responses of gypsum exclusive
131 vs. generalist species to three intensities of livestock pressure to assess whether gypsum
132 exclusive species might be favoured at higher grazing levels and to detect traits that best
133 explain plant responses to grazing. To this end, we sought response to three specific
134 questions. First, dominant species on gypsum soils differ in response to livestock
135 pressure in terms of their relative abundance? We expected differences among species
136 depending on their affinity to gypsum soils (Braun-Blanquet and Bolòs 1958).
137 Consequently, we hypothesised that gypsum exclusive species would tend to be more
138 resistant to moderate grazing (i.e. increase or maintain their relative contributions to
139 vegetation cover) than generalist species. Second, are responses of gypsum exclusive
140 and generalist species to livestock grazing associated with traits such as canopy height,
141 canopy area, leaf C, leaf N, leaf S, specific leaf area (SLA) and leaf dry matter content
142 (LDMC) along a grazing intensity gradient? We expected that gypsum exclusive species
143 would show avoidance strategies to herbivory, and thus, they would invest more in
144 defences, such as greater leaf S content and tougher leaves (i.e., lower C and lower
145 LDMC), than generalist species, as Cera et al. (2021) proposed. Third, do species
146 differing in their vulnerability to sheep grazing pressure (i.e., affecting their relative

147 abundance) vary in key traits along livestock pressure gradients on gypsum soils?
148 Following the growth-defence hypothesis (Herms and Mattson 1992), species capable
149 of increasing or maintaining their relative abundances along a grazing intensity gradient
150 could be either tolerant, responding to biomass offtake by rapid growth (i.e., high N,
151 low C), or avoider species, investing in defences (i.e., high leaf S, low SLA, low
152 LDMC) instead of growth.

153

154 **Material and methods**

155 *Study site, grazing gradient and selection of species*

156 The Middle Ebro Valley, mainly comprising the province of Zaragoza (north-eastern
157 Spain, 41°39'00" N; 0°53'00" W) is one of the most arid regions in Spain, covering an
158 area of ca. 200 km by 80 km (Braun-Blanquet and Bolòs 1958). This region has
159 extensive gypsum soils and a semi-arid Mediterranean climate with mean annual
160 temperature of 14.9 °C and mean total annual rainfall of 354 mm (data from Farlete
161 weather station; 41°50'56" N, 0°30'19" W; 1982–2012 period). Gypsum outcrops in this
162 area consist mainly of low hills (on average 480 m a.s.l.) and flat-bottomed valleys
163 (Foronda et al. 2019). The patchy vegetation is composed of shrubs, forbs and grasses
164 (Guerrero-Campo et al. 1999). The area has a history of extensive livestock rearing,
165 although grazing has been much reduced during the last decades in most areas (Braun-
166 Blanquet and Bolòs 1958; Pueyo et al. 2008).

167 In 2018, we carried out a plant survey to quantify the effect of sheep grazing on
168 14 plant species dominant on gypsum soils. We selected three localities near Mediana
169 de Aragón (41°27'30"N, 0°45'31"W) where three levels of herbivory (low, medium,
170 high) could be identified (Figure 1). The selection was carried out by interviewing local

171 farmers (e.g., Pueyo et al. 2013). In each of the three locations, we selected a sheep
172 shelter with 900-1200 sheep per shelter (Moret-Fernández et al. 2021). Sheep are
173 overnighed in the shelters and thus areas near the shelters represent high grazing. Areas
174 away from the shelter are grazed during the winter months; sheep graze freely over
175 large areas and represent medium pressure with an estimated density of 0.3 sheep ha⁻¹
176 (Pueyo 2006). Finally, we selected a site at each location where there had been no
177 livestock over the past few decades, hereafter referred to as low grazing pressure.
178 We randomly established 35 2 m × 2 m plots within each site at each location, so that a
179 total of 315 plots (3 locations × 3 sheep intensities × 35 plots) were surveyed. We
180 recorded 52 species across all plots, from which a subset of the 14 most dominant
181 perennial species were selected for the current analysis (Table 1). All 14 species were
182 present at three levels of grazing intensity and accounted for 75.6 % of total plant cover.
183 We classified species according to their affinity to gypsum soils (Mota et al. 2011) as
184 gypsum exclusive (four species) and generalist (10 species). Gypsum affinity was
185 assigned by a group of experts on the gypsum flora of the Iberian Peninsula using the
186 Delphi technique (Turoff and Linstone 1975). This classification is widely used for
187 Iberian gypsum plants (Palacio et al. 2007, 2022; Luzuriaga et al. 2020). We also
188 gathered information on the growth habit and spinescence of all species from Flora
189 Ibérica (Castroviejo et al. 1986).

190

191 *Plant survey and traits*

192 In each plot of the three localities, we recorded species occurrence and estimated plant
193 cover visually. At one locality we also measured in each site several leaf traits (SLA,
194 LDMC, and N, C and S content) and two canopy traits (canopy height and area) during

195 March (forb species) and June (grass species) 2019, concurring with the peak of
196 vegetation development before they started flowering. Within these sites, five different
197 healthy adult individuals per species with foliage exposed to full sunlight were selected.
198 On each of these individuals, canopy height and maximum canopy perpendicular
199 diameters were measured from which canopy area was estimated as an ellipse. Mature,
200 non-senescent and undamaged leaves were also collected from each individual for
201 measurement of leaf traits.

202 Specific leaf area (SLA) was measured as the area of a single side of a fresh leaf
203 (cm^2), including petioles, divided by its oven-dry mass (g), expressed in $\text{cm}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, while
204 leaf dry matter content (LDMC) was estimated as the oven-dry mass (mg) of a leaf,
205 divided by its fresh water-saturated mass (g), expressed in mg g^{-1} (Pérez-Harguindeguy
206 et al. 2016). To measure leaf area, images of leaves were captured with a leaf area meter
207 (STD4800, Regent Instruments Inc., Québec City, Quebec, Canada) and processed
208 using WinFolia (Regent Instruments Inc., Québec City, Quebec, Canada). SLA and
209 LDMC were measured on 10 leaves from each sampled individual. To assess the N, C
210 and S concentrations in leaves, leaf samples were dried to a constant weight at 50 °C
211 during five days and subsequently finely ground using a ball mill (Retsch MM200,
212 Restch GmbH, Haan, Germany) before analysing with an elemental analyser. N
213 concentrations were analysed by EEZ-CSIC Analytical Services (TruSpec CN, LECO,
214 St. Joseph, MI, USA), while C and S concentrations were measured by IPE-CSIC
215 Analytical Services (TruSpec CNS, LECO, St. Joseph, MI, USA). N, C and S
216 concentrations were analysed separately to relate leaf N with maximum photosynthetic
217 rate and SLA (Wright et al. 2004; Pérez-Harguindeguy et al. 2016), leaf C with leaf dry
218 matter and C investment (Pérez-Harguindeguy et al. 2016), and leaf S with
219 specialisation to gypsum soils (Cera et al. 2021).

220 *Statistical analyses*

221 To evaluate the response of plants to sheep grazing in terms of cover for the 14
222 dominant species, we used generalised linear mixed models (GLMM) for each species
223 with sheep grazing as a categorical fixed factor and plot nested within locality as a
224 random factor. We performed Shapiro-Wilk test and visual examination of residuals to
225 check for normality and homoscedasticity of residuals. Models with normally
226 distributed residuals were fitted to a Gaussian distribution with the *lmer* function (Bates
227 et al. 2007), whereas models with non-normally distributed residuals were fitted with
228 *glmer* functions of the ‘lme4’ R package v.1.1-15 (Bates et al. 2007), fitting a different
229 family of GLMM (McCullagh and Nelder 1989) with better AIC (Akaike’s Information
230 Criteria). When differences were statistically significant, we assessed multiple
231 comparisons among levels of fixed factors with the *emmeans* function of the ‘emmeans’
232 R package v.1.4-13 (Lenth et al. 2020). After these analyses, results were used to
233 classify species into three groups in terms of their response to sheep grazing (which
234 includes strategies related to tolerance and avoidance to grazing). This classification
235 was based on the statistical differences in plant cover among the three levels of sheep
236 grazing (e.g., Noy-Meir et al. 1989; McIntyre and Lavorel 2001; Garnier et al. 2018). In
237 the absence of differences, they were classified as species whose cover values remained
238 constant along the grazing gradient. If differences were significant, they were classified
239 as increasing in cover when the estimate was positive, and as decreasing in cover when
240 the estimate was negative. We used this classification in subsequent analyses to better
241 understand differences in functional traits (Table 2), and, jointly with the bibliography,
242 to discuss whether a trait reflects a tolerance or avoidance strategy.

243 To assess differences between gypsum exclusive and generalist species in
244 canopy and foliar traits along the sheep grazing gradient, we carried out GLMM for

245 each trait as the dependent variable with sheep grazing intensity, gypsum affinity and
246 the interaction between them as fixed factors. We added taxonomic family and species
247 nested within family as random factors to avoid phylogenetic bias. When differences
248 were statistically significant, we assessed multiple comparisons among levels of fixed
249 factors as described above. To assess differences between gypsum exclusive and
250 generalist species, we evaluated differences in canopy and foliar traits among species
251 that remained constant, increased or decreased in cover along the herbivory gradient
252 using GLMM. In this case, we included sheep grazing and response to sheep grazing
253 groups as fixed factors, and family and species nested within family as random factors.
254 All statistical analyses and graphics were made using R v.4.0.2.

255

256 **Results**

257 *Differential response to sheep grazing in species with contrasting gypsum* 258 *affinity*

259 The four gypsum exclusive species did not decrease their cover with increasing grazing
260 pressure. *Herniaria fruticosa* increased its cover (Figure 2, Table S1), *Gypsophila*
261 *struthium* and *Ononis tridentata* showed no significant change in cover, while
262 *Helianthemum squamatum* increased its cover at the intermediate level of grazing and
263 decreased its cover at the highest level. In contrast, seven of the 10 generalist gypsum
264 species decreased their cover with increasing grazing (most notably from the low to
265 intermediate grazing levels), two, *Brachypodium retusum* and *Linum suffruticosum*, did
266 not change their cover, while *Sideritis fruticosa* increased its cover between the
267 low/medium and highest levels of grazing pressure.

268

269 ***Shifts in species trait values along the grazing gradient***

270 Grazing had an impact on all plant canopy and leaf traits analysed (Figures 3- 4, Tables
271 2, S2-S3). With increasing herbivory intensity plant canopy height and leaf C decreased,
272 and plants had higher leaf N and S concentrations. Grazing also had an impact on SLA
273 and LDMC, but values of these two leaf traits did not show a linear response. At
274 medium intensities, plants generally showed the lowest value of SLA and the highest
275 value of LDMC.

276

277 Gypsum exclusive species always had higher leaf S than generalists, irrespective
278 of grazing intensity (Figure 3, Tables 2, S2). Both gypsum exclusive and generalist
279 groups exhibited higher leaf S at medium and high grazing pressure than at low
280 pressure. In addition, gypsum exclusive species always had lower leaf C than
281 generalists, but both types of species showed a decrease across the gradient, which was
282 sharper in exclusive species. Gypsum exclusive species decreased their LDMC with
283 increasing grazing intensity, while generalists showed a peak in LDMC at medium
284 grazing intensity and similar values at low and high levels of grazing.

285

286 Species whose relative cover increased with grazing intensity showed higher leaf
287 N at high intensity, whereas species with decreased or constant cover showed similar
288 values at the three levels of grazing (Figure 4, Tables 2, S3). Species whose cover
289 decreased with grazing intensity exhibited similar values of SLA along the gradient,
290 whereas the rest of species showed the lowest SLA at medium grazing intensity. In
291 addition, species whose relative cover remained unchanged at different grazing
292 intensities, such as the two gypsum exclusive species *Gypsophila struthium* and *Ononis*

293 *tridentata*, exhibited a greater canopy height than species that increased in cover, while
294 species that decreased showed similar values of LDMC across grazing gradients.

295

296 **Discussion**

297 We evaluated the responses of gypsum exclusive and generalist species across three
298 intensities of sheep grazing pressure to assess whether gypsum exclusive species might
299 be favoured at higher grazing levels and to detect traits that best explained plant
300 responses. Consistent with our hypotheses, gypsum exclusive species tended to be more
301 resistant to moderate grazing than generalist species. These responses were related to
302 the affinity of species to gypsum soils and S accumulation in leaves. Nevertheless, in
303 general, we found that all species showed similar responses involving canopy and foliar
304 traits along the grazing intensity gradient, regardless of their vulnerability to sheep
305 grazing pressure and gypsum affinity.

306 ***Gypsum exclusive species increase their cover at medium grazing intensities or*** 307 ***maintain their cover under increased grazing pressure***

308 Gypsum exclusive species showed good resistance to increased grazing pressure with
309 only one of four of them (*Helianthemum squamatum*) showing a decrease in cover at
310 the highest grazing intensity. In contrast, seven of the 10 generalist species decreased
311 their cover with increased grazing pressure. Gypsum outcrops are mainly open
312 shrublands due to the edaphic and climatic limitations on plant growth (Escudero et al.
313 2015). Such open areas are frequently grazed by wild and livestock ungulates (Asner
314 and Levick 2012; Bakker et al. 2016), as shown in many gypsum areas across the planet
315 (e.g., Braun-Blanquet and Bolòs 1958; Akhiani 2015). Gypsum-adapted species have

316 been historically exposed to ungulate pressure, as these animals have been part of these
317 ecosystems for the past 54 Ma (Gordon and Prins 2019), and to livestock pressure for
318 the last 6,000 years (Balaguer et al. 2014). Hence, gypsum exclusive plants might be
319 expected to have tolerance mechanisms to withstand grazing.

320 The occurrence of gypsum exclusive species on gypsum soils is not fully
321 explained by soil limitations because they are also able to complete their life cycle in
322 calcareous soils (Cera et al. 2021). Our results suggest that grazing by ungulate species
323 also plays a key role in the ecology of gypsum-adapted species, favouring their relative
324 abundance. The impact of grazing could increase the harsh conditions of extreme soils,
325 as described for saline (Bonis et al. 2005), serpentine (Beck et al. 2015) and gypsum
326 soils (Meyer and García-Moya 1989), favouring soil specialists or species adapted to
327 these extreme soils over invasive or generalist species with less tolerance to harsh
328 conditions. However, we found that not all gypsum exclusive species responded equally
329 to sheep grazing pressure. For example, one gypsum exclusive species increased its
330 cover mainly at higher grazing intensities (*Herniaria fruticosa*), two maintained their
331 cover (*Ononis tridentata* and *Gypsophila struthium*) across the different grazing
332 intensities, while *Helianthemum squamatum* increased its cover at medium grazing
333 intensity, but decreased it at the highest intensity. Furthermore, grazing not only
334 favoured gypsum exclusive species. Some of the generalists also increased or
335 maintained their cover in the higher grazing intensity sites, possibly because they might
336 also have become adapted to ungulate pressure by possessing traits that aid endurance to
337 such conditions. While these results indicate an overall low vulnerability of gypsum
338 exclusive species to moderate intensities of grazing, they also point to species-specific
339 responses that go beyond plant affinities to gypsum soils.

340 *Shifts in traits related to sheep grazing intensity levels*

341 We found that gypsum exclusive species always maintained higher foliar S
342 concentrations than generalist species, independently of sheep grazing pressure. Thus,
343 gypsum exclusives are foliar S accumulators (i.e. showing foliar S concentrations above
344 20 mg g⁻¹, Merlo et al. 2019,), a characteristic that has been related to an ability to
345 accumulate sulphates in the leaf vacuole (Cera et al. 2022) and to the production of S-
346 rich secondary compounds, some with a known anti-herbivore role (Ernst 1990;
347 Tuominen et al. 2019). Such accumulation produces alterations in LDMC and leaf C
348 (Cera et al. 2021), as observed in our study, where gypsum exclusive species had lower
349 LDMC and lower C than generalists, regardless of sheep pressure. In the context of
350 limited growth on gypsum soils, the ability to accumulate S as a defence trait may
351 explain why gypsum exclusive species are favoured under herbivore pressure over
352 generalist species that lack this defence strategy. Sulphur accumulation in leaves as an
353 herbivore deterrent trait clearly deserves further study.

354 We expected to identify two groups of grazing resistant species with differences
355 in leaf traits according to a growth-defence model. However, the species studied showed
356 similar responses to grazing in variation of leaf traits, regardless of their cover responses
357 and gypsum affinity. All species, including the less-resistant ones, had lower leaf C and
358 increased leaf N and S contents when sheep grazing pressure increased. This seems to
359 be the main pattern for stress-tolerant species in our study system, as a response to the
360 loss of above-ground biomass. Sheep remove above-ground biomass (lower canopy
361 values in our study), increasing root:shoot ratios and alleviating competition for scarce
362 resources (Palacio and Montserrat-Martí 2007). This effect could lead to relatively more
363 developed root systems in comparison to above-ground structures, promoting an
364 increase of nutrient absorption and leading to higher concentrations of nutrients in

365 leaves (i.e., higher leaf N and S) and lower content of structural compounds in leaves
366 (i.e., lower leaf C) (Grime 2006; Pérez-Harguindeguy et al. 2016). In addition, sheep
367 excretions are known to provide nutrients in a nutrient-limited soil, such as gypsum
368 (Pueyo et al. 2008). We have recently observed that soil N increased with grazing
369 pressure in our study system (Cera et al. 2022b). This effect would favour a higher
370 uptake of N in the most grazed plots, leading to higher foliar N.

371 Surprisingly, values of SLA and LDMC reported in our study did not generally
372 fit with any mechanism related to growth. We might have expected a higher SLA and
373 lower LDMC when grazing increased (Jäschke et al. 2020), as indicators of a
374 compensatory growth strategy based on the leaf economic spectrum (Wright et al. 2004;
375 Pérez-Harguindeguy et al. 2016). However, values of SLA and LDMC at low sheep
376 grazing intensity were higher and lower than expected according to the leaf economic
377 spectrum, respectively. These discrepancies may be explained by the effect of grazing
378 on plant competition for light (Hodgson et al. 2011), although this hypothesis remains to
379 be tested.

380

381 **Conclusions**

382 Grazing may be a significant selective force acting on plants growing on gypsum soils.
383 Overall, our results indicate that plant affinity for gypsum soils may be a strategy to
384 tolerate grazing and highlight the importance of herbivory in the evolution of gypsum
385 soil exclusive species. Future studies should incorporate herbivory as a factor to
386 increase our understanding of the behaviour of gypsum exclusive species, and by
387 extension, of species adapted to extreme soils. It is noteworthy that sulphur (S)
388 accumulation was an important trait in the response to sheep grazing of species growing

389 on gypsum soils, which is a finding that deserves further attention in the future. Finally,
390 we need to elucidate whether S plays an anti-herbivore role, or another potential role,
391 such as enhancing nutrient acquisition in an extreme soil with nutrient imbalances.

392

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397

398 **Notes and contributors**

399 Andreu Cera is interested in the environmental impacts on plant strategies and
400 community assembly.

401 Gabriel Montserrat-Martí's research focuses on ecological strategies of plants in
402 Mediterranean landscapes.

403 Arantzazu L. Luzuriaga is associate professor whose research interests include assembly
404 processes of annual and perennial plant communities in arid and semiarid ecosystems.

405 Yolanda Pueyo is a research scientist with an interest in the dynamics and functioning
406 of semi-arid ecosystems.

407 Sara Palacio is a research scientist with research interests in functional adaptations of
408 plants to extreme environments.

409

410 **Disclosure Statement**

411 No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

412

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427 **Data availability statement**

428 Data and R code for analyses are available in the Supplementary Files

429

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629 Figure legends

630 Figure 1. The studied three-level herbivory gradient on gypsum outcrops, Middle Ebro Valley,
631 Zaragoza, north-eastern Spain (41°39'00" N; 0°53'00" W): no livestock practices for the past
632 few decades representing low sheep grazing pressure (A); winter grazing and an estimated
633 density of 0.3 sheep ha⁻¹ representing medium grazing pressure (B); areas near sheep shelters
634 where sheep overnight representing high grazing pressure (C).

635

636 Figure 2. Mean (\pm SE) cover values (%) for gypsum exclusive and generalist species at different
 637 sheep grazing intensities, Middle Ebro Valley, Zaragoza, north-eastern Spain (41°39'00" N;
 638 0°53'00" W). The top row includes the four gypsum exclusive species; the 10 generalist species
 639 are given below. Letters indicate significant differences among sheep grazing intensities after
 640 multiple comparisons ($P < 0.05$).

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642

643 Figure 3. Mean (\pm SE) for canopy and leaf traits of species with different gypsum affinity at
 644 different grazing intensities, Middle Ebro Valley, Zaragoza, north-eastern Spain (41°39'00" N;
 645 0°53'00" W). Yellow, gypsum exclusive species; red, generalist species. Different letters above
 646 the error bars indicate significant differences among gypsum affinities (exclusives and
 647 generalists) and levels of grazing pressure (low, medium and high) after multiple comparisons (P
 648 < 0.05).

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651

652 Figure 4. Mean (\pm SE) for canopy and leaf traits of species belonging to different grazing
 653 resistance groups (viz. Figure 2), Middle Ebro Valley, Zaragoza, north-eastern Spain (41°39'00"
 654 N; 0°53'00" W). Blue, species that increased (I); yellow, decreased (D); red, remained constant
 655 (C) in cover along the grazing intensity gradient (light to heavy). Different letters indicate
 656 significant differences among levels of grazing intensity (low, medium and high) after multiple
 657 comparisons ($P < 0.05$).

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660

661 Table 1. Characteristics of species included in the study, Middle Ebro Valley, Zaragoza, north-
 662 eastern Spain (41°39'00" N; 0°53'00" W). Species were classified by their gypsum affinity as
 663 gypsum exclusive or generalist species (Mota et al. 2016). The growth habit and presence of
 664 spines are also shown (Castroviejo et al. 1986). Mean (\pm SE) canopy height refer to data collected
 665 at light grazing sites (five replicates per species). Families: ¹ Asteraceae; ² Caryophyllaceae; ³
 666 Cistaceae; ⁴ Fabaceae; ⁵ Lamiaceae; ⁶ Linaceae; ⁷ Poaceae.

	Affinity	Habit	Canopy height (mm)	Spines
<i>Gypsophila struthium</i> L. in Loefl. ²	Exclusive	Erect/tortuous	860.00 \pm 261.44	-
<i>Helianthemum squamatum</i> (L.) Dum.Cours ³	Exclusive	Suberect/cespitose	121.00 \pm 9.14	-
<i>Herniaria fruticosa</i> L. ²	Exclusive	Suberect/prostate	78.00 \pm 4.90	-
<i>Ononis tridentata</i> L. ⁴	Exclusive	Erect	676.20 \pm 64.91	-
<i>Brachypodium retusum</i> (Pers.) P.Beauv. ⁷	Generalist	Rhizomatous	270.80 \pm 67.22	-
<i>Genista scorpius</i> (L.) DC ⁴	Generalist	Suberect/tortuous	630.00 \pm 84.44	Yes
<i>Helianthemum syriacum</i> (Jacq.) Dum.Cours ³	Generalist	Suberect/cespitose	102.00 \pm 7.35	-
<i>Helianthemum violaceum</i> (Cav.) Pers. ³	Generalist	Suberect/cespitose	166.60 \pm 20.48	-
<i>Helichrysum stoechas</i> (L.) Moench ¹	Generalist	Suberect/tortuous	130.00 \pm 15.17	-
<i>Koeleria vallesiana</i> (Honck.) Gaudin ⁷	Generalist	Cespiteose	80.00 \pm 3.16	-
<i>Linum suffruticosum</i> L. ⁶	Generalist	Erect/procumbent	346.00 \pm 22.49	-
<i>Sideritis fruticulosa</i> Pourr. ⁵	Generalist	Erect	158.00 \pm 11.98	Yes
<i>Teucrium capitatum</i> L. ⁵	Generalist	Erect/tortuous	72.00 \pm 2.00	-
<i>Thymus vulgaris</i> L. ⁵	Generalist	Erect/decumbent	229.60 \pm 13.51	-

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668

669 Table 2: ANOVA testing the effects of tolerance to sheep grazing (increasing, decreasing,
670 constant, Figure 1), grazing pressure, gypsum affinity and their interaction for canopy and leaf
671 traits, Middle Ebro Valley, Zaragoza, north-eastern Spain (41°39'00" N; 0°53'00" W). Chi-square
672 values obtained from Wald test based on GLMMs with taxonomic family and species as random
673 factors. The family of error distributions assumed in each model is also indicated. Asterisks
674 indicate different levels of significance: *** ($P<0.001$), ** ($P<0.01$), * ($P<0.05$), ns (non-
675 significant).

	Family GLMM	Grazing pressure	Gypsum affinity	Sheep resistance	Grazing × Affinity	Grazing × Resistance
Canopy height	Gamma	34.30***	4.29*	16.44***	20.35***	19.84***
Canopy area	Gamma	31.41***	0.05 ^{ns}	4.96*	27.46***	182.61***
SLA	Gamma	58.13***	2.54 ^{ns}	5.76 ^{ns}	12.5**	22.87***
LDMC	Gamma	41.03***	5.14*	2.45 ^{ns}	32.28***	30.66***
Leaf C	Gamma	20.99***	7.63**	3.94 ^{ns}	8.15*	12.84*
Leaf N	Gaussian	23.75***	0.63 ^{ns}	0.77 ^{ns}	0.48 ^{ns}	23.89***
Leaf S	Gamma	27.87***	12.73***	2.42 ^{ns}	2.68 ^{ns}	3.58 ^{ns}

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